

Further readings

Alger, J., et al. The false promise of deep-sea mining. *npj Ocean sustainability*, 4, 21 (2025). <https://www.nature.com/articles/s44183-025-00127-4>

Blasiak, R., et al. Corporate control and global governance of marine genetic resources. *Science Advances*, 4, eaar5237 (2018) <https://www.science.org/doi/10.1126/sciadv.aar5237>

IPCC Special Report on the ocean and cryosphere in a changing climate (summary for policy makers) - <https://www.ipcc.ch/srocc/chapter/summary-for-policymakers/>

Jones, D.O., et al. Long-term impact and biological recovery in a deep-sea mining track. *Nature*, 642, 112-118 (2025). <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41586-025-08921-3>

Marine sustainability in an age of changing oceans and seas. European Academies, Science Advisory Council (2016). <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC97977>

OECD (2016), *The Ocean Economy in 2030*, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264251724-en>.

OECD (2019), *Rethinking Innovation for a Sustainable Ocean Economy*, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264311053-en>.

Pauly, D., & Zeller, D. (2016). Catch reconstructions reveal that global marine fisheries catches are higher than reported and declining. *Nature Communications*, 10244 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms10244>

Prellezo, R., et al. Building climate resilient, social sustainability and equity of global fisheries. *npj Ocean sustainability*, 2, 10 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s44183-023-00017-7>

Sumaila, U.R. et al. Financing a sustainable ocean economy. *Nature Communication*, 12, 3259 (2021). <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41467-021-23168-y>

Switzerland's maritime strategy 2023-27 - <https://www.eda.admin.ch/eda/en/fdfa/fdfa/publikationen.html/content/publikationen/en/eda/schweizer-aussenpolitik/maritime-strategie-2023-2027>

The United Nations Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development (2021–2030) - <https://oceandecade.org>

United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS) – BBNJ Negotiations - <https://www.un.org/bbnj/>